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ACADEMIC COMMENT

About 25% of all schizophrenic patients may be misdiagnosed and instead suffer from juvenile dementia

Abstract

A minority of neurologists is convinced that the disease "dementia praecox" first described by Emil Kraepelin in 1899 is still valid and its annexation by psychoanalysis and later by psychiatry has caused severe damage. The psychoanalytic extremist Eugen Bleuler had successfully annexed all conceivable mental conditions for Freud's couch therapy and had withdrawn them from medical research by his own postulates, which could never be proven. A recent further study now supports Kraepelin's once discarded thesis in a new way. This gives rise to a commentary by physicians on the clinical front.

Comment

Dementia praecox ("juvenile dementia"), a term coined by German psychiatrist Emil Kraepelin around 1899, refers to a disorder that begins in late adolescence and includes symptoms that ultimately lead to dementia (in the sense of a total mental destruction), along with delusions. The term dementia

praecox was soon after merged with what we know today as schizophrenia, a term introduced in the year 1911. For 110 years neurologists and psychiatrists have been arguing against and among each other whether this combination was correct, or, on the contrary, a means of obscuring - and thus missing out on research into - a catastrophic disease. The proponents of the

doctrine that Kraepelin got it wrong have now become more and more under fire. Rightfully so. Not only since the discovery of anti-NMDA receptor encephalitis and similar disorders, the melting pot "schizophrenia" is wobbling. Now, an analysis of MRI scans with artificial intelligence has provided further evidence for the existence of juvenile dementia.

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The subtle changes that occur in the brain of many patients diagnosed with schizophrenia resemble the early stages of frontotemporal dementia, the researcher's AI system found. Since affected patients often have an unfavorable course with severe cognitive dysfunction, the study's astonished authors wonder if psychiatrist Emil Kraepelin was right after all with his concept of dementia praecox more than a century ago.

As specialists for rare neurological disorders, this does not surprise us. If anything, we are surprised that the new study has surprised so many colleagues in the clinical and the scientific community.

Patients who develop psychosis in young adulthood can be helped quite well with medication. The antipsychotics do not cure true (!) schizophrenia, but the patients learn to live with their attenuated hallucinations and other psychiatric symptoms. In other patients, however, the cognitive disturbances worsen, eventually looking like, and in fact being, a form of dementia.

It was precisely for these patients that Emil Kraepelin had coined the term dementia praecox in 1899, before scientific vanity simply wiped away "his" disease. The emerging psychoanalysis sect wanted the definitional sovereignty for the brain and dementia praecox became a victim of this unscientific annexation. Psychoanalysis extremist Eugen Bleuler was the champion of this misguided denial of dementia praecox, which continues to cause distress and suffering today. Kraepelin correctly described that adolescent dementia is due to a disturbance in the frontal and temporal lobes of the brain, which fully explain the

changes in personality, social behavior, thinking, memory, perception, empathy, and so on. It is not only possible but an obvious fact that those patients in whom Kraepelin diagnosed dementia praecox suffered from juvenile frontal-temporal dementia (FTD). FTD, like Alzheimer's, is a neurodegenerative disease. In a certain form of frontotemporal dementia, the behavioral variant (bvFTD), psychotic symptoms are common. These patients are often initially misdiagnosed with schizophrenia, or to be more precise, misdiagnosed as psychiatric patients.

Now, a team from "Max Planck Institute for Human Cognitive and Brain Sciences" in Leipzig, Germany, has investigated whether a software based on multimodal machine learning can distinguish between the two disorders when analyzing magnetic resonance images. This was based on measuring the gray matter of the brain, which slowly declines in the affected regions in FTD. Result: 41% of schizophrenia patients were recorded as bvFTD patients. These "schizophrenia patients" diagnosed as bvFTD were often those who did not respond to usual medications. For the researchers, this explains why the condition of some patients with incipient symptoms of schizophrenia, such as hallucinations, delusions and cognitive deficits, had not improved after two years, while others who were just as bad at the beginning were able to continue their education and could become socially integrated again.

The researchers carefully hint towards the idea that Kraepelin was essentially correct in his concept of dementia praecox almost 125 years ago, at least in some patients. In the beginning, similar neuronal structures are affected in both diseases. These are, for example, the "default mode" network and the salience network of the brain, which are responsible for attention control, empathy and social behavior. Unfortunately, the researchers obviously did not dare to be more specific in their paper.

Medicine is still a very conservative science and no physician or medical field changes his/her/its concepts easily. However, the study describes that their software can predict if patients with "schizophrenia" are

likely to develop a severe course because they show typical bvFTD patterns on MRI. Or, as every truly independent researcher would state: because these patients don't have schizophrenia but juvenile dementia praecox. In these patients, it might be worthwhile to initiate intensive therapeutic support at an early stage, the two psychiatrists explain in their paper. In the long term, new therapies could possibly be developed for this group of patients. However, it would be interesting to learn which "therapeutic support" can stop a dementia.

Therefore, one should and must postulate: Emil Kraepelin was right, and about 25% of all rather young patients diagnosed with schizophrenia actually suffer from juvenile frontotemporal dementia. This would lead to more adequate strategies for the care and nursing of these patients, who usually already suffer from the full-blown dementia around the age of 30.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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